

A Physics-Driven Spectroscopic Approach for Rapid Estimation of the Soil Water Retention Curve

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Why Soil Water Retention Curve (SWRC) Is So Important?

Measuring SWRC Is Never Easy!

HYPROP

WP4

Pressure Plate

Reflectance Spectroscopy

Sadeghi et al. (2018)

Water Effects on Soil Reflectance Spectra

- Water molecules are strong absorbers of light.
- Soil reflectance decreases with soil moisture.

Water Effects on Soil Reflectance Spectra

Where Is the Effect of Water Structure?

We **hypothesize** that soil reflectance vary significantly not only with soil water content, but also with **soil water structure around soil particles**.

Partitioning between capillary and adsorbed water requires the knowledge of SWRC

Research Objectives

1. Derivation of a more accurate moisture-reflectance functional relationship.
2. Estimating the SWRC parameters inversely from moisture-reflectance data.

Theory

Lebeau and Konrad (2010)

$$\theta = \theta_c + \theta_a$$

$$\theta_c = \frac{1}{2} \theta_s \operatorname{erfc} \left[\frac{\ln(h/h_m)}{\sqrt{2}\sigma} \right]$$

$$\theta_a = \theta_o \left(1 - \frac{\theta_c}{\theta_s} \right) \left(1 - \frac{\ln|h|}{\ln|h_d|} \right)$$

$$(\theta_o, h_m, \sigma)$$

Theory

Experimental Data

Soil textures of the 21 investigated AZ source soils based on the USDA soil classification scheme.

Soil Water Retention

Tempe cells (Soil moisture Equipment Corp., Santa Barbara, CA, USA).

WP4

AQUALAB Vapor Sorption Analyzer
(METER Group, Inc., Pullman, WA, USA)

Experimental Data

LabSpec® 2500 spectroradiometer (ASD Inc., Longmont, CO, USA)

Results and Discussion

We hypothesize that soil reflectance vary significantly not only with soil water content, but also with **soil water structure around soil particles.**

$$r = \frac{(1 - R)^2}{2R}$$

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Theory

Kubelka – Munk Two-Flux Model

$$r = r_d + \overbrace{c_a \theta_a}^{r_a} p_a + \overbrace{c_c \theta_c}^{r_c} p_c$$

(θ_o, h_m, σ)

Model in Inverse Mode

$$r = r_d + c_a \theta_a^{p_a} + c_c \theta_c^{p_c}$$

Summary and Conclusions

- Capillary and adsorbed components of soil water impact soil reflectance differently.
- A new physical model allows rapid estimation of the soil water retention curve.
- The model only requires soil water content dependent reflectance data, which can be obtained in 3-4 hours.

Papers

Contents lists available at [ScienceDirect](#)

Journal of Hydrology

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/jhydrol

Research papers

A novel laboratory method for the retrieval of the soil water retention curve from shortwave infrared reflectance

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ARTICLE INFO

This manuscript was handled by Corrado Corradini, Editor-in-Chief, with the assistance of Renato Morbidelli, Associate Editor

Keywords:

Laboratory method
Soil water retention curve
Soil hydraulic properties
Shortwave infrared reflectance
Optical proximal sensing

ABSTRACT

The soil water retention curve (SWRC) is an essential soil property that relates soil water content and matric potential. It plays a crucial role in soil water dynamics and the understanding of various hydrological phenomena at the land surface, including infiltration, runoff, evaporation, and energy exchange processes. In recent years, proximal sensing methods have shown great potential for retrieving this challenging-to-measure property from spectral reflectance. However, a physically-based approach is still lacking as current methods rely on empirical data-driven algorithms. Here we propose a novel physics-based laboratory method that, for the first time, enables direct estimation of the entire SWRC from saturated to dry using soil water content/reflectance data pairs within the shortwave infrared domain. The main hypothesis underlying the new method is that soil optical properties not only vary with soil water content but also with the pore scale distribution of capillary and adsorbed soil water. For evaluation, retrieved soil water retention curves of 21 soils that vastly differ in physical and hydraulic properties were compared to direct measurements. The results suggest that the new method is a rapid and efficient alternative to established laboratory measurement methods.

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Research papers

A novel physical-empirical model linking shortwave infrared reflectance and soil water retention

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Soil reflectance
Hydraulic soil properties
Soil water retention
Optical remote sensing

ABSTRACT

Soil hydraulic properties, including soil water retention, control various terrestrial hydrological processes such as infiltration, runoff, and evapotranspiration. Measuring and monitoring these properties at large scales is challenging. Therefore, over the past decade, remote sensing has been investigated as a promising tool for large-scale mapping of soil hydraulic properties. Nonetheless, a solid physical relationship between soil hydraulic and spectral properties is still lacking. To close this knowledge gap, this study introduces a novel physical-empirical model that to our best knowledge for the first time connects the soil water retention curve (SWRC) to soil spectral reflectance. The new model has been developed based on the hypothesis that the capillary and adsorbed water components of the SWRC exhibit vastly different optical properties due to their distinct distribution within the soil porous system. The model was validated using soil water retention and reflectance measurements of 21 soils, vastly differing in physical and hydraulic properties. The model provides not only a new and accurate soil moisture-reflectance functional relationship, but also a potential means for retrieval of the soil water retention curve from spectral reflectance in the shortwave infrared domain.

Thank You for your Attention!

THANK YOU

Any Questions?